

Conference Abstract

Distribution of cave-dwelling pseudoscorpions (Arachnida) in Brazil

Diego Monteiro von Schimonsky[‡], Maria Elina Bichuette[§]

[‡] Faculdade de Filosofia, Ciências e Letras de Ribeirão Preto - FFCLRP - USP, Ribeirão Preto, Brazil

[§] Universidade Federal de São Carlos, São Carlos, Brazil

Corresponding author: Diego Monteiro von Schimonsky (dmvschimonsky@gmail.com)

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Abstract

Pseudoscorpions are one of the most diverse of the smaller arachnid orders but there is relatively little information about the distribution of these tiny animals, especially in Neotropical caves. Here we map the distribution of the Pseudoscorpiones in Brazilian caves with record of 12 families and 22 genera, total 313 caves from 13 states. Among them, two families (Atemnidae and Geogarypidae) with three genera (*Brazilatemnus* Muchmore, 1975, *Paratemnoides* Harvey, 1991 and *Geogarypus* Chamberlin, 1930) are recorded for the first time in cave habitat as well as other seven genera previously unknown for Brazilian caves (*Opiolum* Beier, 1931, *Pachyolpium* Beier 1931, *Tyrannochthonius* Chamberlin, 1929, *Lagynochthonius* Beier, 1951, *Neocheiridium* Beier 1932, *Ideoblothrus* Balzan, 1892 and *Heterolophus* Tömösváry, 1884) but these genera are from families already recorded in this habitat, and have their distributional ranges expanded for all other previously recorded genera. We present these data in maps, considering the biogeographical provinces. For the genus *Spelaeoernes* Mahner, 2001, we re-evaluate its Schiner-Racovitza status and propose the troglobite status. Finally, we discuss the ranges of the pseudoscorpion families/genera for Brazilian caves (Suppl. material 1).

Keywords

biogeographical provinces, cave fauna, Neotropical, Pseudoscorpiones

Presenting author

Maria Elina Bichuette

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Supplementary material

Suppl. material 1: Distribution of cave-dwelling pseudoscorpions (Arachnida) in Brazil

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